

Fire Up the Dialogue

D2.2: REPORT ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE DISCUSSION FORMATS I

Project: **Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management**

Acronym: **Firelogue**

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CONTENT

List of Figures.....	4
List of Abbreviations.....	5
Executive summary	7
1 Introduction.....	8
2 Implementation of Knowledge Exchange Formats	9
2.1 Annual (digital) Conference Clustering Event.....	9
2.1.1 Follow-up of the Clustering Event 2022: collaboration and roadmap development.....	9
2.1.2 Clustering Event 2023.....	11
2.2 Joint Impact Assessment Workshops.....	12
2.3 Peer Review Programme.....	13
3 Additional formats.....	14
3.1 Basis for Knowledge Transfer	14
3.2 Research Integration Board (RIB).....	15
3.3 WFRM Governance Linking research with policy frameworks.....	15
3.4 FIRE-RES Open Innovation Challenge	16
3.5 Green Deal Support Office	16
4 Conclusion and Outlook	17
5 References.....	18
6 Appendix.....	19
Appendix I – Roadmap developed with the IAs	19
Appendix II – Agenda for the Clustering Event 2023	21

List of Figures

Figure 1: Screenshot of the interactive WFRM Case Studies map on the Lessons on Fire – powered by Firelogue platform.....	10
Figure 2: Registration page for the DRMKC Annual Seminar and the WFRM Clustering Event.....	12
Figure 3: Firelogue Project Map.....	14

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
AGIF	Agência para a Gestão Integrada de Fogos Rurais
BG	Break-out Group
DoA	Description of Action
DRMKC	European Commission Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre
IA	Innovation Action
REA	Research Executive Agency
TS	Thematic Strand
UCPM	EU Civil Protection Mechanism
WFRM	Wildfire Risk Management
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
Consortium Partners	
ADAI	Association for the Development of Industrial Aerodynamics
CMCC	Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici
CTFC	Consorti Centre de Ciència i Tecnologia Forestal de Catalunya
EDGE	EDGE in Earth Observation sciences Monoprosopi IKE
FhG	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft für Angewandte Forschung e.V. (FhG)
IIASA	International Institute of Applied System Analysis
INESTEC	Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Tecnologia e Ciência
KEMEA	Centre for Security Studies
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
PCF	Pau Costa Foundation
SAFE	SAFE Cluster
TIEMS	The International Emergency Management Society
TRI	Trilateral Research
UAH	Universidad de Alcalá

VOST	Virtual Operations Support Team from Portugal
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Executive summary

The report aims to delineate the facilitation of knowledge exchange and cooperation among various stakeholders within the Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM) community. It outlines a range of formal and informal knowledge-sharing formats to bridge existing gaps and promote collaboration. The report further provides an overview of the implementation of discussion formats designed to foster cooperation and dialogue among participants, including the three Innovation Actions (IAs), Working Groups (WG), and the wider WFRM community.

1 Introduction

With the overarching goal of enhancing wildfire risk management (WFRM) practices, Firelogue places a strong emphasis on fostering dialogue and cooperation among diverse stakeholder groups. Recognising that collaboration does not always come naturally, this report delves into the implementation of discussion formats within the project, aimed at bridging gaps, promoting knowledge exchange, and advancing WFRM efforts. Firelogue, with its innovative approach, envisions a dynamic space where partners, stakeholders, and experts from various corners of the WFRM community converge to share insights, discuss progress, and forge synergistic partnerships. The present report embarks on an exploration of the three core discussion formats envisioned within Firelogue: the (hybrid/digital) annual conference, joint impact assessment workshops, and the peer review program. These formats serve as platforms designed to facilitate meaningful exchanges, provide insights into the status quo of the projects, and lay the groundwork for future endeavours. Deliverable 2.1 already outlined a number of envisioned discussion formats; the following report will thus present first results of the discussion formats and reflect on possible alternatives. As the report delves into the details of each format, it also casts an outlook into the future, suggesting ways to further enhance their implementation and impact. Flexibility, inclusivity, and adaptability emerge as recurring themes, ensuring that these formats remain responsive to evolving circumstances and the diverse needs of stakeholders. In essence, this deliverable serves as a vital component for promoting cooperation, knowledge sharing, and collaboration among various stakeholders in the WFRM International Community. By identifying information gaps, implementing diverse discussion formats, facilitating exchange between IA study sites, and supporting knowledge transfer, this task contributes to the project's overarching goal of enhancing wildfire risk management efforts and resilience.

2 Implementation of Knowledge Exchange Formats

The task 2.1 “Conceptualisation of IA discussion formats” involves the design and implementation of a variety of knowledge sharing formats, such as meetings, webinars, workshops and more. These formats are intended to bring together IAs and FirEUrisk, as well as the broader network of wildfire-related research projects and the wider WFRM community. The following section will give an overview of the results of the three different knowledge exchange formats as specified in Deliverable 2.1.

2.1 Annual (digital) Conference | Clustering Event

2.1.1 Follow-up of the Clustering Event 2022: collaboration and roadmap development

In April 2022, the first Firelogue annual conference (Clustering Event) took place, inviting representatives from the Innovation Actions, other Horizon 2020 projects and members of the WFRM community to come together and connect with each other, building on synergies between projects as well as common interests. The event was described in more detail in D2.1 “Report and materials for discussion formats” submitted in May 2022. It was detailed that, building on the D1.1 survey across the IAs and FirEUrisk, and initial discussions with the projects, the following thematic break-out groups were developed (the two facilitating organisations responsible are indicated in square brackets):

- Impact Assessment (towards Green Deal 2030 targets) [NOA + UAH]
- Research Integration (Fuel Maps, Fire Event database, others) [ADAI + FHG]
- Knowledge Management on research results and WFRM practices [IIASA + TRILATERAL]
- Case study collaboration and exchange [Pau Costa + FHG]
- (Technical) exploitation | legacy uptake [FHG + INESCTEC]
- Communication & Dissemination incl. Joint Events [NOA + EDGE]

After the Clustering Event, these groups have continued to work together and to further cooperation. For example, the **Impact Assessment** group, coordinated by NOA, meets every three months to discuss the different approaches to assessing the projects’ expected impacts. The work of the Joint Impact Assessment group is also further detailed in Section 2.2. The **Research Integration** group has met twice after the Clustering Event and advances discussions across the projects specifically on assessing risks, as further specified in Section 3.2. The **Knowledge Management** group did not meet again but activities related to knowledge management between the projects were specified and also linked to other Firelogue activities such as the development and population of the Firelogue platform. Some activities that were specifically crafted to cater for upcoming exchange needs are described in Section 3. The **Case Study group** continues to offer support on case study work. Based on the requests of the group members, a joint map of case studies was created and is accessible via *The Lessons on Fire – powered by Firelogue platform* (see Figure 1 below).

Figure 1: Screenshot of the interactive WFRM Case Studies map on the Lessons on Fire – powered by Firelogue platform

It not only shows the individual locations of any case study and give more details, but also promotes the idea that in some locations, projects might be able to combine their efforts to conduct joint exercises actions, thus limiting resources needed and maximizing their impact. More effort is planned for the year to come in combining the mapping with the Peer Review (Section 2.3). Already, at a higher level, Firelogue is actively involved in planning processes on this issue: At the Green Deal Support Office, the “Climate Change and Biodiversity” Working Group, Firelogue is taking the lead on the initiative named “Case Studies Mapping”. The goal of this initiative is to avoid doubling efforts and instead create a platform that contains a wealth of information, including details about partners, technology readiness levels (TRL), stakeholders, and more. This platform will not only focus on geographical aspects but also aims to provide the highest level of exploitability. Here, Firelogue is strongly emphasizing the importance of case study sustainability within this initiative. Firelogue has proposed an annual internal exchange program to facilitate learning from common challenges and mistakes encountered during the project.

The **(Technology) Exploitation group** did not meet again (yet) due to the fact that the projects had not advanced enough in their developments to benefit from such an exchange. The group will be re-activated in 2024. The **Communication & Dissemination** group meets virtually every quarter to harmonize their communication and dissemination approaches. They jointly created the “#EUFireProjectUnited” dynamic initiative which promotes cooperation and exchange between all wildfire projects across social media and joint communication and dissemination actions. It further gives visibility to the projects’ results and actions and creates greater awareness for a holistic WFRM approach. This work is also further detailed in the WP6 Deliverables and more specifically in the Mid-term-report (D6.5).

In addition to the continued exchanges facilitated by Firelogue as detailed above, an overview of Deliverables and timelines were collected from the IAs and FirEUrisk and were translated into a joint **roadmap** (see Appendix II). This roadmap does not only serve as a plan for collaboration but also highlights the (timing of) Deliverables between the projects, e.g., related to their impact assessments.

Table 1 below summarises the targets that the roadmap foresees for the collaboration of the projects under the above specified collaboration topics. The targets envisaged until the end of 2023 have been completed. For the communication, dissemination and joint events, all ongoing activities have been specified in the Communication and Dissemination mid-term report (D6.5).

Table 1: Targets defined for the cross-project collaboration in the Roadmap

Activity	Time-line
<i>Impact Assessment</i>	
Contextualisation of the impacts for the IAs as expected by the Green Deal call	Short term (until February 2023)
Development of a monitoring mechanism for the expected targets	Mid-term (until the end of 2023)
Assessment of individual WFRM measures' impact towards these targets	Long-term (until the end of 2024)
<i>Research Integration</i>	
Development of a European Fuel Map	Mid-term (until the end of 2023)
Development of a shared taxonomy	Mid-term (until the end of 2023)
Development of a European Fire Event database	Long-term (until end of 2024)
<i>Knowledge Management</i>	
Development of a WFRM Knowledge Management Platform	First version until mid of 2023 and further improvement until end of 2025
<i>Case study collaboration</i>	
Case study data base	Mid-term (until mid-2023)
Exchange formats	Mid-term (mid-2023) to long-term (until end of 2025)
<i>Technical exploitation</i>	
Legacy uptake	Short-term (until mid-2023)
Identification of challenges and stakeholder engagement	Mid-term (until the end of 2023)
Exploitation events	Long-term (until end of 2025)
<i>Communication and dissemination incl. joint events</i>	
Joint events	Ongoing, until end of 2025
Website and platform	Ongoing, until end of 2025
Common communication activities	Ongoing, until end of 2025

2.1.2 Clustering Event 2023

The next iteration of the annual conference will take place on 22nd November 2023 in a hybrid format. The event will take place physically in Brussels while the plenary session will be live-streamed. In order to maximise the event's impact and further promote connectivity with other projects, the conference is being hosted and organised in conjunction with the DG ECHO's UCPM Knowledge Networks 7th

DRMKC Annual Seminar on 21st November 2023. The registration is organised jointly as also shown in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Registration page for the DRMKC Annual Seminar and the WFRM Clustering Event

In addition, the meeting of the Expert Group on Forest Fires is taking place on 23rd November, allowing the Member States' experts to potentially also participate in the Clustering event and hence enhancing the exchange between science, policy and practice. Similar to the first event, the aim is to facilitate networking and dissemination while also advancing discussions on dedicated topics such as assessing wildfire risk or enhancing policy coherence. The programme hence envisages a number of presentations by the IAs and FirEurisk as well as by DG ECHO wildfire projects and input to wildfire risk governance aspects by AGIF (on the Landscape Fire Governance Framework) and DG ECHO (on the Wildfire Peer Review Assessment Framework). In addition, several break-out groups and workshops are planned. The detailed agenda can be found in Appendix II.

2.2 Joint Impact Assessment Workshops

The Joint Impact Assessment group meetings have continued in a 3-month interval in digital form with representatives of Innovation Actions. Discussions are focussed on how the projects can effectively assess the impact of their work towards the targets specified by the call such as 0 fatalities or 50% emission reductions from wildfires by 2030, amongst others.

Up until summer 2023, the group has additionally collaborated on a context paper, discussing not only the achievability and desirability of the targets but also the options to monitor the targets in terms of indicators and data availability. In addition, the IAs have sketched their impact assessment approaches. The context paper is expected to be circulated to the European Commission soon and to be further discussed during the Clustering Event in November of 2023 in the context of the Impact Assessment breakout-group. A journal publication on developing and measuring targets for WFRM is planned for 2024.

As next steps, joint workshops will continue happening once every 3 months with the goal to converge towards a homogeneous methodology that capitalizes on the best practices and insights from all the

impact Assessment methodologies that will be followed within the IAs. The goal is to present to the Commission a well-reasoned recommendation on the most effective path forward. More information can be found in D3.4 Impact assessment methodology harmonisation II.

2.3 Peer Review Programme

The Peer review programme, as outlined in deliverable 2.1, has not yet been implemented. While initially, the idea had been to develop the Peer Review around scientific topics¹, during 2023 the idea to structure it around case studies was developed and supported by the IAs. This approach will be referred to as "peer learning programme" to better conceptualise it as a supportive activity of the experienced case study leader in the case study collaboration and to distinguish it from a purely academic review. Since the case studies in the projects under consideration have only just started, the more structured implementation is planned for 2024. In particular, it is planned to have a cross-project exchange of partners to participate in trials, exercises, etc., building on the initial stocktaking of the case studies (see above). Therefore, a regional approach is envisaged. In addition, a meeting with the case study coordinators of the IAs is planned for the end of 2023.

In the past, respective invitations have been shared across the projects in a less structured manner. For example, invitations have been shared by Firelogue on the SAFERS and FIRE-RES events. At the moment, Firelogue supports SAFERS in organizing two (2) webinars, one on "Citizens Participation in Wildfire Risk Management: Examples and Insights" on the 6th of November 2023, and one on "Innovations in Wildfire Risk Management: A Showcase of EU-Funded Project Results" on the 8th of November 2023. Firelogue assists SAFERS with finding supporters and speakers through the #EUFireProjectsUnited initiative. FIRE-RES also reached Firelogue to support their initiative "Open Innovation Challenge". Firelogue, through the #EUFireProjectsUnited initiative, communicated the event to all the communication Teams of several projects (SILVANUS, TREEADS, SAFERS, FIREURISK, PYROLIFE, FIRE-ADAPT). Firelogue supported also FIRE-RES by creating relevant posts for social media.

¹ The Impact Assessment group for example provides a forum for peer learning. However, this exchange is already taking place anyhow. Peer learning and review will furthermore be organised through webinars (see section 3.6).

As a next step, a similar map is planned for mapping the organisations involved in the projects in relation to the stakeholder clustering (cf. D7.7). In this way, it will be easy for organisations to identify their peers and to better link the stakeholder types with the Firelogue working groups and the related development of policy recommendations.

3.2 Research Integration Board (RIB)

The Research Integration Board is organised in a dedicated Task in Firelogue (Task 2.5). It has met in autumn 2022 and 2023 to discuss with the Innovation Actions, FirEURisk and also additional fire projects matters and potential next steps. The main topics for research integration are thereby:

- Risk assessments incl. modelling and fuel mapping
- Case study exchanges and (cross-)validation of mapping approaches
- Contributions to integrated WFRM

The details of these activities will be described in D2.11 (Summary Report of Research Integration Board II). However, it is important to note that the discussions around the mentioned topics are also integrated into the Clustering Events and linked with dedicated activities on advancing WFRM governance (see next section).

Finally, key publications such as the FirEURisk publication by Emílio Chuvieco et al. on Integrated Wildfire Risk Assessment² are shared between the projects through Firelogue mailing lists.

3.3 WFRM Governance | Linking research with policy frameworks

The publication of policy frameworks related to wildfire risk management such as the Landscape Fire Governance Framework³ that was presented during the International Wildland Fire Conference in Porto as well the Wildfire Peer Review Assessment Framework by DG ECHO, both in May 2023, stressed the need for specifying the IA and FirEURisk contributions towards these frameworks. Consequently, the European Research and Innovation event on Disaster management, Security, Defence and Infrastructure Protection which took place on Rhodes on 29-31 May 2023 was used to start the related discussions. FirEURisk, together with Firelogue, hosted a workshop on wildfire risk management that was attended by all IAs, NEMAUSUS and SAFERS, as well as speakers from the European Commission's side. Initial thoughts about differentiating *integrated* and *holistic* WFRM were shared and the projects' contributions towards enhanced WFRM governance were sketched. The conference discussions were followed-up by a digital meeting in August 2023 and translated into a dedicated session during the Clustering Event 2023 on wildfire risk governance.

Work on the topic will continue, and an entire conference Track on Integrated WFRM which was submitted by Firelogue to ISCRAM 2024⁴ has been accepted. The track foresees the implementation of the following sessions:

- Upscaling Integrated Wildfire Risk Management: the governance perspective
- Innovative tools and approaches for enhancing Wildfire Risk Assessment
- Risk evaluation and tolerance

² Chuvieco et al (2023): Towards an Integrated Approach to Wildfire Risk Assessment: When, Where, What and How May the Landscapes Burn, *Fire*, 6(5), 215; <https://doi.org/10.3390/fire6050215>.

³ Landscape Fire Governance Framework, p. 3 ([64df3d8c07e6565f7631b8c9_Framework_AGIF - ENG V2.pdf \(website-files.com\)](https://www.ercis.org/files.com/64df3d8c07e6565f7631b8c9_Framework_AGIF_-_ENG_V2.pdf))

⁴ <https://iscram2024.ercis.org/> (28.09.2023)

- Good management practices for landscape resilience to wildfires
- Multi-stakeholder integration
- Requirements for citizen and media engagement
- Insurance instruments and related technologies for wildfire risk reduction
- Extreme events: new challenges for inter-agency response
- Recovering from extreme events: the need for new restoration and recovery approaches

Under the hashtag #EUFireProjectsUnited, projects are invited to contribute to the sessions and representatives of the projects have already agreed to support the review process of the submissions.

3.4 FIRE-RES Open Innovation Challenge

FIRE-RES is implementing an Open Innovation Challenge which is supported by Firelogue. This is on the one hand done via support on communication activities through social media. On the other hand, it was agreed that the winners of the Challenges and their solutions could be included in the Firelogue platform.

3.5 Green Deal Support Office

In addition, the attendance at seminars and events related to the project area has been used to connect with stakeholders and identify new actors in the field. For example, the Firelogue coordinators were invited to Brussels by the DG's support office to lead the case studies mapping and were able to network with representatives of the RESONATE and SUBERB projects on site.

The stakeholder manager shared the updated stakeholder mapping with the relevant team members, partners and stakeholders themselves to ensure that all stakeholders have access to the latest information. He is also responsible for regular reviews and updates of the stakeholder mapping to ensure that it remains current throughout the life cycle of the Firelogue project.

4 Conclusion and Outlook

The reciprocal exchange of knowledge between the projects in the call and the WFRM cluster is crucial to promote mutual learning and the exchange of ideas. Different workshop formats have been designed, each addressing different thematic issues and operating at different levels of the projects, with the explicit aim of promoting an open and effective dialogue between the actors within the cluster. Thus, the second iteration of the annual conference will be organised to build on the lessons already learned and again provide partners with the opportunity to come together and exchange ideas. The road map that emerged from the thematic focus of the first clustering event has already formulated concrete developments. Joint impact assessment workshops will be organised and conducted, providing a cross-project basis on which to measure project outcomes. By means of a special "peer learning process" in which relevant experts from the field give concrete advice on the ongoing work of the projects, findings can be deepened. Furthermore, additional formats developed around improved knowledge exchange, taking up and continuing existing research results (Research Integretion Board), cooperation in the large EU association (Green Deal Support Office) and the first webinars. The implemented formats will be continued, sharpened and further developed in the coming months as insights from the IAs will continue to grow further.

5 References

Chuvieco, E., et al. (2023). Towards an integrated approach to wildfire risk assessment: when, where, what and how may the landscapes burn." *Fire* 6.5: 215.

Martín, D.; Juan, X.; Vendrell, J.; Prat, N.; Borràs, M. (2023). Stakeholder Clustering Report II. Deliverable D7.7 FIRELOGUE.

Martín, D.; Juan, X.; Vendrell, J.; Prat, N.; Borràs, M. (2022). Stakeholder Clustering Report. Deliverable D7.2 FIRELOGUE.

6 Appendix

Appendix I – Roadmap developed with the IAs

Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM) Project Cluster Roadmap

Introduction

The European Green Deal has made available about 60 Mio. € to respond to extreme wildfire events via funding line LC-GD-1-1 "Preventing and fighting extreme wildfires with the integration and demonstration of innovative means". The three Innovation Actions (IAs) funded under this call are FIRE-RES, SILVANUS and TREEADS. According to the call, the Actions funded "will speed up the pan-European adaptation process to extreme wildfires by advancing and applying research and innovation, including demonstration pilot sites, while making best use of existing data (e.g. remote sensing, in-situ or community-based data), technologies (e.g. Big Data and Artificial Intelligence) and services (as Copernicus, Galileo and EGNOS). Innovative means and methods should be developed, integrated and demonstrated in different environments across Europe (including EU outermost regions) and tailored to geographical and socio-economic conditions, with different types of fuels (e.g. forest/bush /peat fire threats), landscapes and biodiversity values (e.g. coastal/alpine/agriculture/rural/Wild-Urban Interface/islands) and scales (e.g. local/regional /national/cross-border/EU/international). The approach should be systemic: encompassing different climate scenarios, biogeographical/socio-economic contexts, traditional practices and new means for faster and smarter management of all interconnected fire management phases, i.e. prevention and preparedness (including forecasting and landscape management for impact mitigation, adapting tree species composition and forest management practices), detection and response (including fire containment, extinction, potential evacuation and recovery) and post-fire restoration and adaptation to climate change."

The funded projects are expected to contribute the following impacts by 2030:

- 0 fatalities from wildfires
- 50% reduction in accidental fire ignitions
- 55% reduction in emissions from wildfires
- Control of any extreme and potentially harmful wildfire in less than 24 hours
- 50% of Natura 2000 protected areas to be fire-resilient
- 50% reduction in building losses
- 90% of losses from wildfires insured
- 25% increase in surface area of prescribed fire treatments at EU level

In order to work towards these targets, synergies between the projects and their activities, expected outputs and recommendations need to be understood and strengthened. Promising results as demonstrated in the projects need to be identified, upscaled and deployed into climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction strategies, land use policies and spatial planning, in line with EU policy guidelines and legislation, including forest, biodiversity and bio-economy related strategies, the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS) (including forecasts and risk assessments) and the Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre (DRMKC) Risk Data Hub, as well as the Knowledge Centres for Biodiversity and Bioeconomy and the Forest Information System for Europe (FISE) or the

Union Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM) and Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC) to name just a few.

The Firelogue project was funded to support the clustering and cooperation among the projects, the integration of research results and the extensive and structured knowledge exchange to finally ensure that the demonstration of innovative and integrated approaches fulfils the expected impacts. This roadmap has been co-developed with the Innovations Actions funded under the Green Deal WFRM funding line but also with wildfire projects more broadly. It represents a key document for the collaboration over the next years with respect to the strategic collaboration between the projects.

WFRM Clustering event organised by Firelogue

One of the first activities of the Firelogue project was the organisation of a WFRM Project Clustering Event which took place virtually on 5th and 6th April 2022. The Clustering Event addressed to the following projects and was attended by more than 80 experts from the WFRM research domain:

Project(s)	Funding Line	Starting date
TREEADS, FIRE-RES, SILVANUS, Firelogue	Green Deal Call, LC-GD-1-1-2020 - Preventing and fighting extreme wildfires with the integration and demonstration of innovative means	October, November & December 2022
FirEURisk	H2020 – Call 3.5 (Societal Challenges), LC-CLA-15-2020 - Forest Fires risk reduction: towards an integrated fire management approach in the E.U.	April 2021
FIRE-IN	H2020 call 3.7 (Secure Societies), SEC-21-GM-2016-2017 - Pan European Networks of practitioners and other actors in the field of security	May 2017
FireLinks	COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology) Action	October 2018
SAFERS	H2020 – Call 3.5, SC5-16-2019 - Development of commercial activities and services through the use of GEOS and Copernicus data	Oct 2020

A core part of the Clustering Event was organised around six different break-out groups, namely:

- *Impact Assessment (towards Green Deal 2030 targets)*
- *Research Integration (Fuel Maps, Fire Event database, others)*
- *Knowledge Management on research results and WFRM practices*
- *Case study collaboration and exchange*
- *(Technical) exploitation | legacy uptake*
- *Communication & Dissemination incl. joint Events*

The scope of these thematic break-out groups was based on a survey implemented by the Firelogue project, to which the Innovation Actions (IAs) (TREEADS, FIRE-RES, SILVANUS) and FirEURisk had responded. This survey was focused to better understand the projects including their interest for

Appendix II – Agenda for the Clustering Event 2023

Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM) Project Clustering Event 2023 | Integrated Wildfire Risk Management

Purpose: Showcase first project results; exchange about coherence and complementarity between the projects with respect to Integrated WFRM; outreach strategies towards the science-policy-practice communities.

Scope: One full day in person meeting (ca. 09:00-17:30)

Date: 22nd November 2023

Location: Royal Library of Belgium (KBR), Boulevard l'Empereur 2, Brussels 1000, Belgium

Number of participants: ca. 80 from FirEURisk, FIRE-RES, SILVANUS and TREEADS as well as from other projects such as SAFERS, FireLinks, FireAdapt, DG ECHO projects; EGFF members, EC representatives and other guests.

Time	Agenda Item
09:00 – 09:15	Welcome and Introduction
09:15 – 09:30	Keynote on Disaster Resilience: An innovative approach to multi-hazard and multi-risk - the Myriad project (Philip Ward, VU Amsterdam) (requested)
09:30 – 10:15	Overview of the H2020 Fire Projects FirEURisk, FIRE-RES, SILVANUS and TREEADS
10:15 – 11:15	Project pitches by DG ECHO Fire projects (Moderation and introduction by Cristina Brailescu, DG ECHO) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AFAN Project (Jonathan Troncho, Pau Costa Foundation) - IPA Flood and Fires (Agostino Goretti, Protezione Civile, IT) - WUITIPS (Elsa Pastor, Universtiat Politècnica de Catalunya)
11:15 – 11:30	Coffee break

11:30 - 13:15	Integrated Wildfire Risk Governance	
	Discuss approaches to integrated WFR management and governance	
	11:30 – 12:00	Introduction to the topic <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FirEUrisk project results (Domingos Viegas, ADAI) - The Landscape Fire Governance Framework (Tiago de Oliveira, AGIF)
12:15 – 13:15	Break-out groups (Two groups per topic):	
	Assessing and evaluating the risk of fire (Lucrecia Pettinari, University of Alcalá & Domingos Viegas, ADAI)	Governing wildfire risk (George Eftychidis, Aristotelian University of Thessaloniki/ Satways Ltd.& Eduard Plana, CTFC)
13:15 – 14:00	Lunch Break	
14:00 - 14:15	Integration of solutions and project results Firelogue offers (Sofia Oikonomou, EDGE and Claudia Berchtold, FhG) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lessons on Fire by Firelogue platform Technology Mall and solutions registry • Thematic Working Groups approach and the Justice dimension of WFRM 	
14:15 – 15:45	Thematic Workshops	
	Policy recommendations and coherence (Eduard Plana, CTFC) Discuss first/draft recommendations from the projects and their links with EU policies such as Forestry or Adaptation strategies.	Fuel mapping and modelling (Domingos Viegas, ADAI) Present the collaboration between the projects and discuss further synergies as well as the applicability of mapping and modelling approaches; drafting of policy recommendations
	Impact Assessment (Mariza Kaskara, NOA) Present the joint White Paper on the Green Deal targets as well as the projects' impact assessment methodologies: How to compare results across Europe and identify progress on policy targets?	
15:45 – 16:00	Coffee Break	
16:00-16:30	Reports from the break-out groups	

16:30 – 17:15	Projects' solution highlights (Coordinated by Mariza Kaskara, NOA) Note: The solutions presented should highlight how they contribute to a holistic approach of managing wildfires Open to all research projects. Projects can present 2-3 of their solution highlights
17:15 – 17:30	Closing remarks (Moderated by Nicolas Faivre) Note: <i>To be confirmed: take-away messages from the European Commission</i>
17:30 – 19:00	Walking dinner Continuation of informal discussions and solution highlights

THIS IS THE END OF THIS DOCUMENT

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